

From Words to Action: Brand Purpose and Storydoing

Alfonso Freire-Sánchez (Universidad Abat Oliba CEU, *CEU Universities*)

Montserrat Vidal-Mestre (Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona)

Introduction

The relationship between business, society, and communication has been widely examined through the lenses of corporate social responsibility (CSR), social marketing, sustainability, and, more recently, brand activism. In recent years, however, particular attention has been given to a concept that shifts the focus from isolated responsible action to the brand's reason for being and its ability to be translated into verifiable conduct: brand purpose. Unlike approaches focused exclusively on reputation or on specific CSR programs, brand purpose refers to a more structural logic linked to brand identity, social legitimacy, and the consistency between what a brand declares and what it actually does (Tafuro & Piccaluga, 2025; Walter et al., 2024).

The relevance of the concept can be partly explained by a social context in which stakeholders expect organizations not only to be economically effective, but also to make meaningful contributions to social life. *The Edelman Trust Barometer 2025* places business as the most trusted institution globally among the four major institutions analyzed, with a trust index of 62, ahead of NGOs, governments, and the media (Edelman, 2025). At the same time, the *Meaningful Brands 2024* report, produced by Havas and based on more than 156,500 respondents across 24 markets and more than 2,600 brands, confirms that consumers expect brands to make a relevant and tangible contribution to their everyday lives and to society at large (Havas, 2024). Likewise, *Deloitte's global survey* shows that 75% of Gen Z and millennials consider an organization's social and community impact important when evaluating a potential employer, indicating that purpose affects not only the brand-consumer relationship but also talent attraction and organizational legitimacy (Deloitte, 2024).

It is important to clarify that brand purpose is not simply synonymous with CSR (Barrio-Fraile *et al.*, 2024). The recent systematic review by Tafuro and Piccaluga (2025), based on 118 articles, shows that corporate purpose should be understood as a broader strategic and organizational dimension, whereas brand purpose is located more specifically at the level of identity, symbolic mediation, and the relationship between the brand and its stakeholders. This distinction is relevant because it avoids two common reductionisms: on the one hand, confusing purpose with an advertising slogan or a narrative device; on the other, dissolving it entirely into general corporate strategy. From this perspective, brand purpose does not merely consist of expressing abstract values, nor can it be reduced to one-off cause-related marketing campaigns; rather, it operates as an articulating principle linking identity, value proposition, internal culture, and social contribution (Knowles, 2025; Tafuro & Piccaluga, 2025).

Different approaches and relationship with CSR

The growing popularity of the term in professional contexts has led to diverse and often ambiguous interpretations. One of the most widespread links it to Sinek's (2009) *Why*, that is, to the question of the deeper reason why an organization exists. This approach is useful for understanding purpose as an identity-based foundation, but it is insufficient unless it also incorporates a social dimension that can be materialized and assessed. Recent research insists precisely on this shift: the issue is no longer simply to formulate an inspiring purpose, but to ensure that such purpose is translated into decisions, behaviors, policies, and consistent experiences. In this sense, purpose only acquires strategic value when it can be authentically

activated through the brand and through relationships with different stakeholder groups (Knowles, 2025).

For this reason, an important part of the current literature has begun to examine brand purpose in relation to authenticity and the risks of symbolic instrumentalization. Walter et al. (2024), in an experimental study on purpose-driven branding, conclude that a purpose perceived as authentic improves brand credibility, whereas woke washing has a negative effect in comparison with neutral approaches. In the same vein, Ahmad et al. (2024) show that inconsistency between a brand's activist messages and its actual practices gives rise to different forms of woke washing, and that such inconsistency can be especially harmful when the brand communicates commitments that it later fails to fulfill. These studies are particularly useful because they shift the analysis from the content of the discourse to its practical validation: it is not enough to adopt a social cause in brand storytelling; it must be sustained through consistent actions both inside and outside the organization (Ahmad et al., 2024; Walter et al., 2024).

In turn, the review by Luna-Amador et al. (2025) confirms that recent research on brand activism is structured around four major clusters: CSR, social media, brand equity, and authenticity. The authors also identify a transition from approaches closer to CSR toward perspectives in which activism and purpose are integrated into brand identity itself. This observation is relevant for the present study because it helps explain that brand purpose does not necessarily operate as a tactical extension of CSR, but rather as a category more closely related to brand definition and to the legitimacy of its public presence (Luna-Amador et al., 2025). Therefore, it does not seem appropriate to equate BP with corporate vision, occasional philanthropy, or a classical CSR policy. Vision generally refers to a desired image of the future; philanthropy refers to specific contributions, often disconnected from the core business; and CSR is usually articulated through programs, indicators, and actions designed to manage responsibilities and impacts. Brand purpose, by contrast, is situated at a more structural level: it affects the brand's reason for being, guides its discourse, and demands consistency between promise and behavior (Barrio-Fraile et al., 2024). This does not mean that purpose and CSR are independent domains, but rather that they maintain a relationship of partial integration: CSR may be one way of materializing purpose, but it does not exhaust it. When purpose informs the business model, internal culture, and brand experience, it comes closer to the logic of shared value proposed by Porter and Kramer (2011), according to which economic and social value should be created simultaneously rather than as a subsequent form of compensation. This interpretation places BP closer to a strategy of meaning-making, legitimacy, and action than to a sum of disconnected responsible initiatives.

From this perspective, brand purpose may be regarded today as a distinct analytical category within contemporary strategic communication. Its relevance lies not only in its ability to provide the brand with a differentiating narrative, but also in its potential to articulate a shift from storytelling to storydoing (Freire, 2017), that is, from the narrative formulation of a reason for being to its translation into observable and sustained practices. For this reason, it is pertinent to examine the extent to which brand purpose can be differentiated from CSR and social marketing, under what conditions it generates shared value, and when it ceases to be a rhetorical promise and becomes a credible practice.

Brand purpose and storytelling in corporate narrative

Once the main features of brand purpose (BP) have been delimited from different perspectives and its distinctions from CSR have been clarified, it becomes necessary to introduce another key variable: the contemporary consumer or user. Earlier categorizations such as digital immigrant and digital native helped explain the first stages of the digital

transition (Prensky, 2011; Tomé, 2011), but they are now less analytically useful in a media environment characterized by platform convergence, constant connectivity, participatory culture, and algorithmically mediated interactions. In the current context, what matters less is whether users belong to one generational category or another and more whether they are able to interact with brands critically, publicly, and continuously across multiple touchpoints. This shift has transformed the relationship between companies and audiences, moving it away from a purely transactional logic and toward a more relational and dialogic model based on experience, interaction, emotional connection, and mutual expectations (Gobé, 2005; Freire, 2017). Recent research confirms that digital environments have intensified the value of narrative, participation, and brand meaning in shaping consumer perceptions and engagement (Kaur et al., 2024; Zimand-Sheiner, 2024).

As a result of this transformation, consumers increasingly evaluate brands not only according to the utility of their products or services, but also according to how they behave, what they stand for, and what kind of impact they generate in society. This broader evaluative framework helps explain why many organizations have adopted more explicitly human, value-oriented, and socially responsive forms of positioning. In earlier work, this tendency was associated with emotional branding and more humanized brand relations (Gobé, 2005), whereas current literature frames it in terms of purpose-driven branding, authenticity, and engagement. Recent global data support this shift. The Meaningful Brands 2024 report shows that people expect brands to contribute meaningfully to their lives and to the wider social environment, while the 2025 Edelman Trust Barometer indicates that business remains the most trusted major institution globally, although this trust is increasingly conditional on visible and credible action (Edelman, 2025; Havas, 2024). Likewise, the Deloitte Gen Z and Millennial Survey 2024 reports that social impact plays a significant role in how younger generations evaluate organizations, including as potential employers (Deloitte, 2024). These findings suggest that the contemporary brand is expected not only to communicate efficiently but also to justify its social relevance.

In this setting, storytelling becomes a central mechanism through which brand purpose can be made intelligible, emotionally resonant, and socially shareable. It is not enough for an organization to define a purpose; it must also communicate that purpose in ways that foster recognition, identification, and involvement among stakeholders. Earlier contributions already emphasized the managerial and persuasive power of stories, particularly their ability to overcome reductionist forms of communication and to appeal to audiences through complete and meaningful narrative structures (Simmons, 2006; Freire, 2017). More recent research reinforces this view. Studies on digital storytelling show that narrative elements such as coherence, thematic consistency, sensory evocation, and experiential framing contribute positively to brand image and audience evaluation (Kaur et al., 2024). Similarly, corporate brand storytelling research has proposed multidimensional models in which story, meaning, ritual, and transmedia articulation work together to strengthen stakeholder relationships and extend brand narratives across platforms (Zimand-Sheiner, 2024).

From this perspective, storytelling should not be understood merely as an expressive or decorative device, but as a strategic instrument for translating purpose into a narrative universe that users can recognize as credible and worth engaging with. This point is especially relevant because the effectiveness of purpose communication depends not only on emotional appeal but also on perceived authenticity. Research has shown that authentic storytelling improves brand evaluations and contributes to the communication of brand value, whereas inconsistencies between narrative claims and organizational behavior can damage credibility (Yin et al., 2023; Walter et al., 2024). In parallel, studies on purpose-driven and activist branding have shown that symbolic appropriation of social causes without substantive

backing may generate accusations of woke washing and weaken stakeholder trust (Ahmad et al., 2024; Walter et al., 2024). Consequently, storytelling is most effective when it does not simply embellish a corporate message, but rather articulates a purpose that is already embedded in organizational culture, business practice, and stakeholder relations.

It follows, therefore, that having a brand purpose is not sufficient in itself; brands must also be capable of involving audiences and moving them through stories that connect purpose with lived experience. In this sense, storytelling can be regarded as one of the most appropriate vehicles for communicating BP because it enables brands to create coherent narrative worlds in which values, actions, and expectations are brought together. Yet contemporary research also suggests that the evolution of brand communication goes beyond storytelling alone. The emphasis is increasingly placed on forms of storydoing, that is, on the translation of narrative into observable practices, participatory experiences, and socially meaningful action. Narrative transportation, visual storytelling, social media interaction, and consumer-generated narratives all contribute to this dynamic by turning stakeholders into co-interpreters and, at times, co-producers of brand meaning (Nikulina et al., 2024; Pereira et al., 2024; Can et al., 2025). Accordingly, corporate narrative is no longer constructed exclusively by organizations, but emerges from the interplay between brand discourse, stakeholder participation, and public validation.

For this reason, the case of La Fageda remains particularly relevant. It represents a form of purpose-driven organization whose social mission preceded the popularization of the term brand purpose and whose corporate narrative developed from a real founding story and a tangible social project rather than from a later reputational strategy. Its case therefore allows researchers to identify those elements that currently support the development of a purpose-driven brand and to examine how such elements can be integrated into corporate narrative not as a short-term tactic, but as a long-term strategic orientation. From this standpoint, the study of La Fageda offers a useful framework for understanding how purpose, storytelling, authenticity, and social value can converge in a credible brand narrative.

Objectives

The general objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To analyze the concept of brand purpose within social marketing strategies and to distinguish it from CSR actions.
2. To examine the relationship between brand purpose and storytelling in order to determine whether storytelling is the most appropriate means of explaining and conveying purpose to consumers.

These general objectives are complemented by the following specific objectives related to the case study:

1. To determine, on the basis of the case study, whether it is necessary to update the four classical stages of branding proposed by Keller (2005) and Kotler *et al.* (2018).
2. Through the case of La Fageda, to identify the narrative elements that function as instruments for communicating brand purpose to stakeholders.
3. To assess whether the brand story through which La Fageda explains its brand purpose follows the narrative pattern of the hero's journey.
4. To establish the relationship between storytelling and the practical enactment of brand purpose, identifying the principles under which it is carried out and the ways in which it is communicated.

Methodology

This exploratory study was developed in two stages.

In the first stage, sources and materials were examined in order to differentiate brand purpose from CSR and from broader corporate values within brand management, thereby situating the concept within the current social marketing landscape. This phase enabled the construction of the theoretical framework, the conceptual delimitation of the term, and the identification of the relationship established with consumers and users through the creation of a corporate narrative by means of storytelling, understood as a mechanism capable of generating emotional involvement and stakeholder engagement.

The second stage consisted of a qualitative case study analysis of La Fageda's corporate narrative (Escudero et al., 2008). Since La Fageda does not rely on advertising campaigns, paid media, or direct marketing actions, and instead bases its communication on content creation, brand value, and earned media, the analysis focused on its discourse and corporate narrative: its messages, its story, and the structure of its brand narrative from the origins of the social enterprise to the present.

The first step in the analysis involved examining what others say about La Fageda through earned media and publicity, that is, information originally disseminated by the company and subsequently reproduced by one or more media outlets. To this end, archival material from newspapers, magazines, television programs, interviews, and documentaries was collected and reviewed. Among the sources analyzed, particular attention was paid to several high-profile national media texts with broad public impact, including Jordi Évole's report for *Salvados*, *La Fageda, cuando negocio y ética van de la mano* (La Fageda: When Business and Ethics Go Hand in Hand) (Salvados, 2012); Risto Mejide's interview with Cristóbal Colón for *C de C* (2016); the feature on La Fageda produced by *La Aventura del Saber* for La 2; the documentary *Yogurt Utopia* (2018), produced by TV3; and *La Fageda: Turn the World Outward* (2019), produced by The Arbinger Institute. In addition, the study examined the way the company represents itself through its own media channels, especially the video guide used for visitors to the farm, its corporate website, and branded content such as the video report *La fàbrica de La Fageda per dins* (Inside La Fageda's Factory) (La Fageda, 2021).

To analyze discourse and corporate narrative in relation to La Fageda's brand purpose, the study applied the narrative model of the hero's journey, originally developed by Joseph Campbell and later adapted by Christopher Vogler in *The Writer's Journey*. This methodological approach made it possible to assess whether the corporate narrative built around La Fageda's social project follows the same structure or pattern that underlies most heroic narratives and, therefore, whether it enables a recognizable and natural form of cognitive assimilation both for the target audience of the social project and for the intended audience of the business model.

La Fageda: What is its brand purpose?

To paraphrase the economist Juan Antonio Segarra, the story of La Fageda is unique and difficult to replicate. Located in the Garrotxa region of Catalonia, in northeastern Spain, La Fageda is a social enterprise engaged in the production of dairy products such as yogurt, desserts and ice cream, as well as jams and other food products. From its origins, however, what has made *La Fageda* distinctive is not only the artisanal nature or perceived quality of its products, but the fact that its business structure was created in the service of a clearly defined social mission rather than the other way around (La Fageda, 2025a, 2025b).

Unlike many organizations that later adopt a purpose-driven discourse in response to social or reputational pressures, *La Fageda* was born from a pre-existing and explicit purpose: the

social and labor inclusion of people with intellectual disabilities, severe mental health conditions, and, more recently, individuals in situations of social vulnerability (La Fageda, 2025a; The Arbinger Institute, 2019). In this sense, its brand purpose is not an added layer of communication but the foundational logic of the organization itself. As Cristóbal Colón, the founder of La Fageda, has repeatedly argued, the business model is a means to achieve the real end, which is the social project (C de C, 2016).

This principle has important implications for understanding the relationship between purpose and business practice. Because *La Fageda* operates as a non-profit social project with a strong productive structure, its economic results are reinvested in infrastructure, training, support services, and improvements in working and living conditions for the people linked to the project. According to its 2024 Sustainability Report, 651 people were linked to the organization in 2024, 64% of whom belonged to vulnerable groups; the average workforce was 345 employees, including 150 workers with disability certificates employed through the Special Employment Centre and 168 people receiving supported employment services (La Fageda, 2025a). These figures confirm that La Fageda's purpose is not merely declared but institutionally embedded.

Its communication strategy

According to Colón, *La Fageda* “does not do advertising or promotions” (C de C, 2016). Since its origins, its communication strategy has not been based primarily on explicitly promoting its social project, but rather on the quality and taste of its products. This is a relevant strategic point: La Fageda did not position itself in the market by appealing to compassion or solidarity, but by creating a competitive, differentiated product capable of earning consumer recognition on its own merits. In this sense, the social project was not used as a direct sales argument, but as the foundation that made the business model meaningful and sustainable (C de C, 2016; La Fageda, 2025a).

Historically, *La Fageda* first sold milk and later developed a nursery business linked to reforestation. After the transformation of the dairy sector following Spain's integration into the European Economic Community and the imposition of milk production quotas, the organization reoriented its model toward value-added dairy products. In 1993, it launched its artisanal yogurt, which initially entered Catalan hospitals and later expanded into retail and supermarket channels. This shift proved decisive, since it enabled the organization to create a differentiated market position while remaining faithful to its social purpose (C de C, 2016; La Fageda, 2025a).

Over time, as product recognition grew, *La Fageda* gradually opened its facilities to the public, allowing visitors to discover the social purpose underpinning the business model. What had initially been informal access later became a structured visitor service, with guided visits booked through the website and designed as immersive experiences combining explanation, observation, tasting, and audiovisual storytelling. According to the organization's official visitor information, *La Fageda* currently receives more than 40,000 visitors each year, and these visits function as a major vehicle for communicating the project without relying on paid advertising (La Fageda, 2025c). In this way, the organization's communication strategy is largely built on product quality, earned media, direct experience, and narrative transmission rather than on conventional promotional investment.

Brand storytelling

La Fageda emerged from the personal motivation of its founder and co-founder, Cristóbal Colón, to improve the lives of people with severe mental health conditions and intellectual disabilities. Before founding the organization in 1982, Colón had spent approximately a

decade working in psychiatric institutions, where he became aware of the lack of labor opportunities, social recognition, and dignified living conditions available to many patients at the time. According to *La Fageda's* own historical account, this experience became the trigger for a project grounded in the conviction that meaningful work can be a powerful tool for personal transformation (La Fageda, 2025a). From this perspective, *La Fageda's* corporate narrative is rooted in a clear founding motive: the belief that work dignifies people and enables social inclusion. Colón came to understand that one of the main barriers to integration was the absence of employment opportunities, since people were neither recognized as capable workers nor valued as socially useful individuals. On that basis, he decided to invest in a farm and dairy production so as to create real jobs for people who had traditionally been excluded from the labor market. With the support of Carme Jordà and other partners, the initiative gradually expanded and gave rise to the project that would later become La Fageda (La Fageda, 2025a; The Arbinger Institute, 2019).

The development of *La Fageda's* brand story also includes a key moment of disruption and adaptation. The introduction of milk quotas and the weakening of the reforestation nursery business threatened the viability of the original model. Rather than abandoning the project, the organization transformed this crisis into an opportunity by converting milk surplus into artisanal yogurt production. This strategic pivot not only preserved the organization's continuity but also reinforced its narrative coherence: the social mission remained constant, while the productive model evolved in order to sustain it. In this sense, the organization's storytelling is not merely retrospective but closely tied to resilience, reinvention, and long-term consistency.

Today, *La Fageda* presents itself as a socio-business project whose mission is to improve the quality of life of people in vulnerable situations in the Garrotxa region through work, support, and meaningful inclusion (La Fageda, 2025b). In narrative terms, this means that its corporate story has reached a stage of maturity in which business objectives and brand purpose are fully integrated. The organization's story no longer operates only at the level of communication; rather, it is enacted in concrete structures, services, labor practices, and stakeholder experiences. For that reason, *La Fageda* can be interpreted not only through the lens of storytelling, but also through storydoing, insofar as its founding narrative has been translated into sustained organizational reality.

Narrative elements of storydoing

Once *La Fageda's* brand storytelling has been analyzed and its practical embodiment established, it becomes possible to identify the main narrative elements that structure its storydoing.

1. Cristóbal Colón's personal brand: The founder and long-time visible leader of *La Fageda* plays a central narrative role in the construction of the brand. He was not only the person who conceived the social idea on which La Fageda's purpose is based, but also the figure who most clearly articulated the project's meaning in public. His professional background, oratory, charisma, and personal values are deeply intertwined with the brand's identity. In this respect, the founder functions as both narrator and symbolic embodiment of the brand's purpose, to the point that La Fageda's history has long been publicly understood through his voice and testimony (C de C, 2016; Salvados, 2012).
2. The naming of *La Fageda*: The organization takes its name from La Fageda d'en Jordà, the beech forest located in the Garrotxa volcanic area. This place is not simply a geographical reference but part of the organization's narrative universe. It evokes nature, rootedness, environmental respect, craftsmanship, and a sense of local

belonging, all of which reinforce the symbolic personality of the brand and support its broader discourse of dignity, care, and connection with the land (La Fageda, 2021, 2025b).

3. The creative concept: Unlike other organizations with a social dimension, *La Fageda* has not used labor inclusion as a direct sales pitch. Instead, it has built its market proposition around product quality and differentiation. As Risto Mejide observed in his interview with Colón, consumers do not buy La Fageda “out of solidarity or pity, but because of what you do” (C de C, 2016). This is a key narrative element because it prevents the social mission from being reduced to a sentimental appeal and instead frames it as a source of legitimacy and coherence behind a genuinely competitive product.
4. The visitor experience (user’s journey): *La Fageda*’s visitor service is one of the most important spaces in which its storydoing becomes tangible. The organization has designed a visitor journey that includes the farm, the animals, the production process, guided explanations, an audiovisual presentation of the brand story, and a final product tasting. According to the official website, this service attracts more than 40,000 visitors annually and is explicitly presented as a way of explaining both the project and its products (La Fageda, 2025c). From a narrative perspective, the visit operates as a 360-degree brand experience in which purpose is not merely told but staged and lived through sensory, spatial, and emotional cues.
5. Brand purpose and founding principles: Although La Fageda does not invest heavily in advertising and does not use its social mission as a conventional selling argument, that mission remains the central narrative unit across its media visibility, documentaries, interviews, and branded content. In other words, brand purpose is the axis from which the organization’s founding story, public identity, and non-paid communication are structured. It is the principle that unifies the founder’s story, the company’s discourse, its earned media presence, and the experiences offered to stakeholders. For this reason, La Fageda offers a particularly clear example of how brand purpose can function as the organizing core of a long-term corporate narrative rather than as a short-term communication device (La Fageda, 2025a; The Arbinger Institute, 2019).

Discussion and conclusions

Los resultados permiten dar respuesta a los interrogantes iniciales. Primeramente, se ha comprobado que el propósito de marca (BP) no es una acción de RSC, sino se trata de la razón por la que existe una organización, entidad o empresa. En segundo lugar, a diferencia de la RSC o de una estrategia de marketing social que está vinculada a un posicionamiento y unos objetivos SMART, el propósito de marca es inherente a la propia marca, no está temporizada y no se basa en acciones puntuales que buscan un resultado concreto. En lo que refiere a la aplicación del Viaje del Héroe (Campbell; Vogler,) a la narrativa empresarial vemos que se cumple en los siguientes parámetros:

1. La llamada a la aventura: el leit motiv del impulsor, Cristóbal Colón: ayudar a personas con discapacidades diferentes y enfermedades mentales severas a través de la inserción laboral.
2. El mundo ordinario: la sociedad los rechaza, no les da oportunidades.
3. Rechazo a la llamada: dificultades iniciales, falta de recursos y apoyos.
4. Encuentro con el mentor: no se ha detectado un mentor, no obstante, en la historia se narra el encuentro con el alcalde de Olot para buscar ayudas y apoyos.

5. Aliados y enemigos: Recibe el apoyo de socios y de la psicóloga Carmen Jordà, que acaba convirtiéndose en cofundadora. En la narración no se habla de enemigos, pero sí de la primera impresión de los ciudadanos que era de rechazo o cierto desprecio. En la entrevista con Risto Mejide (CdC, 2016), citan textualmente que decían de la granja que era “el lugar donde los tontos van a pasar la tarde”. Por tanto, se presenta un enemigo claro: la inadaptación o rechazo social.
6. Cruzar el umbral. El punto de inflexión es la fundación de La Fageda que, en primera instancia, era una exportadora de leche de vaca.
7. La cueva oscura. El momento más duro fue la imposición de los límites de productividad de leche por parte de la Unión Económica Europea a lo que se añadía la escasez de demanda de los viveros para la reforestación.
8. La gran prueba. Se concreta en 1983 con el lanzamiento del yogurt artesano.
9. La recompensa. Reciben los primeros reconocimientos de los hospitales catalanes por la calidad del producto conseguido.
10. El camino de vuelta. La empresa se transforma, empieza a distribuirse en miles de comercios y cientos de supermercados de toda Cataluña.
11. Resurrección. La Fageda sobrevive a la crisis económica del 2011, al aumento de la competencia en marcas de distribución, al hecho que otras marcas también han creado productos artesanos y otras vicisitudes del mercado. No solo se mantiene, sino que aumenta su oferta de productos y cada vez es una marca más reconocida y con mayor reputación y valor de mercado.
12. Vuelta con el elixir. La Fageda consigue realizar el propósito de marca con el que había nacido, dando trabajo a unas 400 personas con discapacidades diferentes, enfermedades mentales y personas en riesgo de exclusión. No obstante, la historia no ha llegado a su fin y la organización sigue trabajando cada día en este propósito.

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